

AniDMS: Estimating dimethyl sulphide (DMS) across North

Atlantic over 20 years with machine learning

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Abstract. Existing dimethyl sulphide (DMS) products are too coarse in space and time (≥ 25 km, monthly) to support movement-scale analysis of seabird olfactory navigation. This leads to a geospatial mismatch between environmental representations and individual movement trajectories. We developed a machine-learning framework that combines multi-source data harmonisation, spatio-temporal interpolation, and stacking-based ensemble prediction to reconstruct daily DMS fields at 4km resolution across the North Atlantic. Six base learners were evaluated and integrated using an ElasticNet stacking design. The final model achieved strong performance (test $R^2 = 0.88$; RMSE = $0.859 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$), outperforming previously reported basin-scale approaches. The resulting product captures seasonal cycles, persistent hotspots, and fine-scale gradients. We further developed AniDMS, an open-source Python tool for automated retrieval of gridded DMS data and reproducible annotation of trajectories with DMS. A Manx shearwater case study demonstrates the integration of a dynamic DMS surface with movement data. This work provides a transferable geospatial workflow for reconstructing high-resolution environmental fields and linking them to tracking data.

Submission Type. Model; Dataset; Algorithm; Software.

BoK Concepts. [AM14] Generalization and aggregation; [GC1] Geocomputation and complex systems; [GD3] Transaction management of geospatial data.

Keywords. dimethyl sulphide, machine learning, ensemble method, olfactory navigation

1 Introduction

Research on animal navigation has traditionally focused on visual and geomagnetic cues. In contrast, olfactory navigation, in which animals use air-borne odours as navigational cues, remains comparatively underexplored. This is because spatially explicit odour datasets are largely absent from ecological research, since biological evidence is sufficient (Gagliardo and Bingman, 2024).

This limitation is especially pronounced in seabirds. *Procellariiform* species possess highly developed olfactory systems, and experimental work demonstrates that odours play an essential role in their navigation process over the open ocean (Gagliardo *et al.*, 2013). Among potential chemical cues, dimethyl sulphide (DMS), a climatically active sulphur compound produced by phytoplankton through marine biogeochemical processes, has emerged as a key compound linking ocean productivity, atmospheric chemistry and seabird behaviour (Nevitt and Bonadonna, 2005). However, DMS remains poorly characterised in space and time from a movement-ecological perspective.

Most existing DMS products operate at monthly temporal resolution and coarse spatial scales, failing to capture the dynamic odour landscapes encountered by migratory birds (Wang *et al.*, 2020). This absence represents a central methodological barrier to testing olfactory navigation at larger scales.

We address this gap by (i) developing an ensemble modelling framework that stacks six base learners with an ElasticNet to produce a daily, kilometre-scale DMS

dataset across the North Atlantic, and (ii) introducing AniDMS, an open-source Python toolkit for annotating animal movement trajectories with these DMS estimates.

2 Methods

2.1 Data and Preprocessing

The study domain covers the North Atlantic (80°W-15°E). Model training and evaluation were conducted using in situ DMS observations (0°-75°N) from the NOAA PMEL global database and the NASA NAAMES regional cruise dataset (2002-2024). Due to persistent limitations in satellite ocean colour retrieval at high latitudes during winter, the final predicted DMS product is restricted to 0°-60°N, corresponding to the primary activity range of most North Atlantic pelagic seabirds.

Five environmental predictors were selected based on previous DMS modelling studies: chlorophyll a (CHL), mixed layer depth (MLD), sea surface temperature (SST), nitrate (NO₃), and photosynthetically available radiation (PAR). Satellite-derived predictors were obtained from Copernicus, ESA, and NASA platforms and harmonised to a daily temporal resolution. All spatial operations were performed in a Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area projection and feature values were obtained by spatio-temporal interpolation.

2.2 Machine Learning Framework

We evaluated six machine learning models representing complementary paradigms: XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin, 2016), LightGBM (Ke *et al.*, 2017), Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), Support Vector Regression (Drucker *et al.*, 1996), Gaussian Process Regression (Rasmussen and Williams, 2008), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (Rumelhart, Hinton and Williams, 1986). The dataset was split into training (70%) and test (30%) subsets, and predictors were standardised prior to model fitting. Hyperparameters were optimised using grid search with five-fold cross-validation.

To integrate complementary model strengths and improve generalisation, we implemented a stacking ensemble framework. Final model performance was evaluated using RMSE and R², and predictor contributions were analysed using SHAP to assess nonlinear dependencies. The trained ensemble model was then applied to generate daily DMS dataset at 4 km resolution across the North Atlantic for 2002-2024.

2.3 Data and Software Availability

The DMS dataset generated in this study is publicly available via Zenodo under an open-access license

(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18615736>). AniDMS is distributed as an open-source Python package and can be installed via both PyPI and Conda-forge. The full source code, including AniDMS, machine-learning models, and all data processing workflows, is publicly available on GitHub to enable reproducible research: <https://github.com/BEGIN-StAndrews/AniDMS>.

3 Results

3.1 Model Performance and Generalisation

We evaluated six base learners and three stacking ensemble models for DMS prediction. Among individual models, tree-based ensembles performed best: Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM achieved test R² values of 0.875, 0.873, and 0.854, with RMSE between 0.88 and 0.95 μmol m⁻³. Kernel-based models and the neural network showed lower predictive skill (test R² < 0.75).

All stacking ensembles improved test performance, but generalisation differed across meta-learners. Ridge and Lasso showed clear overfitting, whereas ElasticNet achieved the best balance between accuracy and generalisation (R² = 0.881, RMSE = 0.859 μmol m⁻³) (Figure 1). Within the operational domain (0-60°N), performance further improved (RMSE = 0.721 μmol m⁻³, R² = 0.915), indicating strong spatial transferability.

Figure 1 Observed versus predicted DMS concentrations across the North Atlantic. Each point represents a DMS measurement.

3.2 AniDMS tool and case study

We developed AniDMS, an open-source Python package for querying daily DMS dataset and annotating movement trajectories by inverse distance weighting. A case study using Manx shearwater tracking data from July 2019 (Figure 2) illustrates fine-scale heterogeneity in DMS exposure along individual movement paths.

Figure 2. Annotated Manx shearwater trajectories by AniDMS.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

No Generative AI tools were used in preparation of this paper.

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